

Generalized Method for Solving Fractional Differential Equations

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Abstract

This paper explores the solution of fractional-order differential equations (where $0 < \alpha < 1$) along with initial conditions using the power series method. A novel technique is introduced to obtain exact solutions for fractional differential equations, which extends to solve integer-order differential equations as well. Additionally, a generalized technique for finite systems is presented, accompanied by numerous examples and applications showcasing our results. The paper also includes graphical representations of the solutions.

Keywords: Gamma function; Mittag-Leffler function; Caputo fractional Derivative; Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative; Fractional differential equations; Power series method.

1. Introduction

derivatives and Integrals are generalized to non-integer orders in fractional calculus. In the past ten years, it has been discovered that fractional calculus is essential to the modeling of a wide range of phenomena, most notably memory-dependent phenomena and complex media like porous media. When studying dynamical systems, fractional calculus has become a valuable and effective tool when using classical methods reveal significant limitations.

Ordinary differentiation and integration are prolonged to any non-integer order in fractional calculus. The topic dates back to the days when differential calculus was created by Leibniz and Newton. It is as old as differential calculus itself. The fractional derivative notion and the precise birthday of the fractional calculus are owed to Leibniz in a letter to L'Hospital dated September 30, 1695. L'Hospital asked the question as to the meaning of $\frac{d^n y}{dx^n}$ if $n = \frac{1}{2}$

i.e., what if n is fractional? Leibniz replied that $d^{\frac{1}{2}x}$ will be equal to $x\sqrt{dx} : x$ 32

Leibniz discussed a potential method for fractional-order differentiation in letters to 33
J. Wallis and J. Bernoulli (in 1697). This is how the definition may be as follows for 34
non-integer values of n .: $\frac{d^n e^{mx}}{dx^n} = m^n e^{mx}$. 35

In 1730, When interpolating between integral orders of a derivative, Euler recommen- 36
ded using the relationship that follows.: 37

$$\frac{d^n x^m}{dx^n} = \frac{\Gamma(m+1)}{\Gamma(m-n+1)} x^{m-n} \quad 38$$

,where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the (Euler's) Gamma function. 39

Over time, a number of well-known mathematicians, including Liouville, Grünwald, 40
Riemann, Euler, Lagrange, Heaviside, Fourier, Abel, and others, laid the formal found- 41
ations for fractional calculus. Numerous eminent mathematicians have since worked on 42
these and related issues, including Laplace, Fourier, Abel, Liouville, Riemann, Grunwald, 43
Letnikov, Levy, Marchaud, Erdelyi, and Riesz. Fractional differential equations are a pop- 44
ular subject in engineering, physics, chemistry, biology, and other disciplines. Fractional 45
differential equations are becoming a very important and popular topic. It is possible to 46
specify the so-called fractional differential equations by extending the normal integer order 47
derivative to any order. Fractional calculus has several uses; some of these are covered in 48
Debnath [6], Kilbas [9], and Podlubny [17]. Fractional differential equations have drawn the 49
attention of numerous scholars, who have used the monotone method in conjunction with 50
lower and upper solutions to successfully establish existence and uniqueness conclusions 51
[7, 11, 12, 13,14, 15, 16]. Historical information on the fractional calculus was provided 52
by Oldham and Spanier [16] and Miller and Ross [13]. The current work is organized into 53
four sections: an introduction; section two provides definitions for the Riemann-Liouville 54
fractional derivative, the Euler Gamma function, and the Mittag-Leffler function; other 55
aspects are also discussed. In part 3, the power series approach is used to solve initial 56
value problems (IVP). Section 4: Solutions are also provided graphically. 57

2. Prerequisites 58

This section outlines fundamental definitions, characteristics, and formulas necessary for 59
understanding the subsequent sections. 60

2.1 The Definition of Gamma Function 61

The Euler Gamma function is denoted by $\Gamma(z)$ and is defined as

$$\Gamma(z) = \int_0^{\infty} x^{z-1} e^{-x} dx, (\Re(z) > 0)$$

where $x^{z-1} = e^{(z-1)\log(x)}$ and $z \in C$, set of complex numbers. 62

For

$$n \in R, \Gamma(n+1) = n!$$

2.1.1 Properties of Euler Gamma Function 63

- $\Gamma(z + 1) = z\Gamma(z), z \in C$ 64
- $\Gamma(n + 1) = n!, n \in N$ 65
- $\Gamma(z)\Gamma(1 - z) = \frac{\pi}{\sin\pi z}$, on -integer $z \in C$ 66
- $\Gamma(n + \frac{1}{2}) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}(2n!)}{2^{2n}(n!)}, n \in N$ 67
- $\Gamma(\frac{n}{2}) = \frac{(n-2)!\sqrt{\pi}}{2^{\frac{n-1}{2}}}$ 68

2.2 The Definition of Beta Function 69

The Beta function is usually defined by 70

$$\beta(z, w) = \int_0^1 \tau^{z-1}(1 - \tau)^{w-1} d\tau, (Re(z) > 0, Re(w) > 0).$$

2.3 The Relation between Gamma and Beta Function 71

The Beta function can also be defined in terms of Gamma Function as 72

$$\beta(m, n) = \frac{\Gamma(m)\Gamma(n)}{\Gamma(m+n)} \quad \text{Where } m, n \in R^+ \quad \text{73}$$

2.4 Mittag-Leffler Function 74

An essential tool in fractional calculus is the Mittag-Leffler function, which is an extension 75
of the exponential function. The function was created by Mittag-Leffler, a mathematician 76
from Scandinavia (1846–1927). We discuss the definitions of the Mittag-Leffler function 77
with one parameter, the two parameter Mittag-Leffler function, and the convolution for- 78
mula for the latter. 79

2.4.1 One-Parameter Mittag-Leffler Function 80

A Single parameter Mittag-Leffler function is denoted by $E_\alpha(z)$ and is defined as 81

$$E_\alpha(z) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^m}{\Gamma(m+1)} \quad (1)$$

Keep in mind that the exponential function e^z . 82

and the hyperbolic cosine function $\cosh z$, respectively, are one parameter Mittag- 83
Leffler functions when $\alpha = 1$ and 2. 84

2.4.2 Two Parameters Mittag-Leffler Function 85

The Mittag-Leffler two-parameter function is represented by 86

$E_{\alpha,\beta}(z)$ and is defined as

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$$E_{\alpha,\beta}(z) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^m}{\Gamma(\alpha m + \beta)}, (\alpha > 0, \beta > 0) \quad (2)$$

Note that exponential function e^z and hyperbolic sine and cosine functions are particular cases of two

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parameter Mittag-Leffler function if $\alpha = 1, \beta = 1; \alpha = 2, \beta = 1$ respectively.

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2.5 Caputo's Fractional Derivative

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The definition of the fractional differentiation of the Riemann Liouville type played an important role in the development of the theory of fractional derivatives and integrals and for its applications in pure mathematics. Caputo's definition can be written as

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$${}^C D_t^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha - n)} \int_a^t \frac{f^{(n)}(\tau) d\tau}{(t - \tau)^{\alpha + 1 - n}}, (n - 1 < \alpha < n).$$

2.6 Riemann-Liouville Fractional Derivative and Riemann-Liouville Fractional Integral

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Let $\alpha \in R$ and $n = [\alpha]$, where $[\cdot]$ is the greatest integer function. The Riemann-Liouville Fractional Derivative of order α is indicated by D^α and

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$$D_a^\alpha y(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \alpha)} \left(\frac{d}{dt}\right)^n \int_a^t (t - \tau)^{n - \alpha - 1} y(\tau) d\tau,$$

$\alpha \leq t \leq b$

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Also, the Riemann-Liouville Fractional Integral of order α is denoted by

$$I_a^\alpha y(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^t (t - \tau)^{\alpha - 1} y(\tau) d\tau.$$

2.6.1 Illustrations

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$$1. D_0^{\frac{1}{2}} C = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2})} \frac{d}{dt} \int_0^t (t - \tau)^{-\frac{1}{2}} C d\tau = \frac{d}{dt} (2C \sqrt{\frac{t}{\pi}}) = \frac{C}{\sqrt{\pi t}}, C \text{ is any constant.}$$

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$$2. I_0^{\frac{1}{2}} C = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2})} \int_0^t (t - \tau)^{-\frac{1}{2}} C d\tau = 2C \sqrt{\frac{t}{\pi}}, C \text{ is any constant.}$$

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2.7 Riemann Liouville Fractional Derivative and Riemann Liouville Fractional Integral of Power Function.

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The power function's Riemann-Liouville Fractional Derivative of order α can be found using the formula

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$${}_a\mathbf{D}_t^\alpha t^\gamma = \frac{\Gamma(1+\gamma)}{\Gamma(1+\gamma-\alpha)} t^{\gamma-\alpha}, \gamma > -1, \alpha > 0. \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, the order Riemann Liouville Fractional Integral of a power function is given by

$${}_a\mathbf{I}_t^\alpha t^\gamma = \frac{\Gamma(1+\gamma)}{\Gamma(1+\gamma+\alpha)} t^{\gamma+\alpha}, \gamma > -1, \alpha > 0.$$

2.7.1 Illustrations

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$$1. \quad {}_0\mathbf{D}_t^{\frac{1}{2}} t^2 = \frac{\Gamma(1+2)}{\Gamma(1+2-\frac{1}{2})} t^{2-\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{\Gamma 3}{\Gamma \frac{3}{2}} t^{\frac{3}{2}} = \frac{8}{3} \sqrt{\pi} t^{\frac{3}{2}} \quad 107$$

$$2. \quad {}_0\mathbf{I}_t^{\frac{1}{2}} t^2 = \frac{\Gamma(1+2)}{\Gamma(1+2+\frac{1}{2})} t^{2+\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{\Gamma 3}{\Gamma \frac{7}{2}} t^{\frac{5}{2}} = \frac{16}{15} \sqrt{\pi} t^{\frac{5}{2}} \quad 108$$

2.8 Properties of Riemann-Liouville Fractional Derivatives

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If $y(t)$ is continuous for $t \geq \alpha$, then the integration of arbitrary real order has the following properties.

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$$1. \quad {}_a\mathbf{D}_t^{-\alpha} [{}_a\mathbf{D}_t^{-\beta} y(t)] = {}_a\mathbf{D}_t^{-\alpha-\beta} y(t) \quad 111$$

$$2. \quad {}_a\mathbf{D}_t^\alpha [{}_a\mathbf{D}_t^{-\alpha} y(t)] = y(t), \text{ for } \alpha > a \text{ and } t > a \quad 112$$

$$3. \quad {}_a\mathbf{D}_t^\alpha [\lambda y_1(t) + \mu y_2(t)] = [\lambda {}_a\mathbf{D}_t^\alpha y_1(t) + \mu {}_a\mathbf{D}_t^\alpha y_2(t)] \quad 113$$

Definition 2.1 One-term equation [17] If there is only one term on the left side of the fractional differential equation then fractional differential equation is called as one-term equation.

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Definition 2.2 Radius of convergence of series [10] The radius of convergence R is a nonnegative real number or ∞ in a way that the series converges if

$$|x - a| < R$$

and diverges if $|x - a| > R$

3. POWER SERIES METHOD

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This section describes how to solve fractional differential equations with various initial conditions using the power series method. The approach to resolving differential equations with fractions that is the clearest is the power series method. The goal is to get the solution in power series form, from which the coefficients need to be ascertained. This technique is widely used to solve applied problems since it can be roughly computed as the partial sum of series. One-term equation with zero, non zero and

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$$[{}_0\mathbf{D}_t^{\alpha-1} y(t)]_{t=0} = \beta$$

, type initial conditions are considered. 117

3.1 One-term equation with zero initial condition 118

Consider the one-term fractional initial value problem 119

$${}_0\mathbf{D}_t^{\alpha-1}y(t) = f(t), y(0) = 0, t > 0, 0 < \alpha < 1. \quad (4)$$

Let 120

$$y(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n t^{n+\alpha} \quad (5)$$

be the power series solution of equation [4]. 121

Suppose that the function $f(t)$ can be expanded in the Taylor series converging for 122

$0 \leq t \leq R$, where R is the radius of convergence: 123

$$f(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{n!} t^n \quad (6)$$

Using equation (5) and (6) in equation (4), We have 124

$${}_0\mathbf{D}_t^{\alpha} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n t^{n+\alpha} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{n!} t^n \quad (7)$$

Applying formula (3), we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n \frac{\Gamma(1+n+\alpha)}{\Gamma(1+n)} t^n = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{n!} t^n$$

Equating coefficients of like powers of t , one can determine the coefficients by formula 125

$$a_n = \frac{\Gamma(1+n+\alpha)}{\Gamma(1+n)} \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{n!} = \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{\Gamma(1+n+\alpha)}, n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (8)$$

Substituting these coefficients in equation (5), the series solution of fractional initial value problem (4) is 126

$$y(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{\Gamma(1+n+\alpha)} t^{(n+\alpha)} \quad (9)$$

Clearly the series converges absolutely with region of convergence $(0, \infty)$ 127

Example 3.1: Consider the one-term fractional initial value problem 128

$${}_0\mathbf{D}_t^{\frac{1}{2}} = cost, y(0) = 0, t > 0. \quad (10)$$

Since $f(t) = cost$, $f'(t) = -sint$, $f''(t) = -cost$, $f'''(t) = sint$, $f^{iv}(t) = cost$, 129

Figure 1: Example 3.1

$$f(0) = 1, f'(0) = 0, f''(0) = -1, f''' = 0, f^{iv}(0) = 1.$$

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Now we determine the coefficient $a_n, n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ by

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$$a_n = \frac{\Gamma(1 + n + \alpha)}{\Gamma(1 + n)} \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{n!} = \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{\Gamma(1 + n + \alpha)}$$

$$a_0 = \frac{f(0)}{\Gamma(\frac{3}{2})} = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{3}{2})}, a_1 = \frac{f'(0)}{\Gamma(\frac{5}{2})} = 0, a_2 = \frac{f''(0)}{\Gamma(\frac{7}{2})} = \frac{-1}{\Gamma(\frac{7}{2})}, a_3 = \frac{f'''(0)}{\Gamma(\frac{9}{2})} = 0, a_4 = \frac{f^{iv}(0)}{\Gamma(\frac{11}{2})} = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{11}{2})}$$

Thus the series solution of fractional initial value problem is

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$$y(t) = a_0 t^{\frac{1}{2}} + a_1 t^{\frac{3}{2}} + a_2 t^{\frac{5}{2}} + a_3 t^{\frac{7}{2}} + a_4 t^{\frac{9}{2}} + \dots$$

$$y(t) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} t^{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{8}{15\sqrt{\pi}} t^{\frac{5}{2}} + \frac{32}{945\sqrt{\pi}} t^{\frac{9}{2}} + \dots \tag{11}$$

Remark 3.1

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If the function $f(t)$ on RHS of (4) has the form $f(t) = t^\beta g(t), \beta > -1$ then also we can discuss the power series method. Assume that $g(t)$ can be expanded in the Taylor series converging for $0 \leq t \leq R$, where R is the radius of convergence, as

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$$g(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{g^{(n)}(0)}{n!} t^n \tag{12}$$

The coefficients $a_n, n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ are given by

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$$a_n = \frac{\Gamma(1 + n + \beta)}{\Gamma(1 + n + \alpha + \beta)} \frac{g^n(0)}{\Gamma(1 + n)} \tag{13}$$

Figure 2: Example 3.2

The series solution of fractional initial value problem (4) is 136

$$y(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(1+n+\beta)}{\Gamma(1+n+\alpha+\beta)} \frac{g^n(0)}{\Gamma(1+n)} t^{n+\alpha+\beta} \tag{14}$$

Example 3.2 : Consider the one –term fractional initial value problem 137

$${}_0D_t^{\frac{1}{2}} = t^2 cost, y(0) = 0, t > 0. \tag{15}$$

Since 138

$$g(t) = cost, g'(t) = -sint, g''(t) = -cost, g'''(t) = sint, g^{iv}(t) = cost,$$

$$g(0) = 1, g'(0) = 0, g''(0) = -1, g'''(0) = 0, g^{iv}(0) = 1.$$

Determine the coefficient $a_n, n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ from (13) as 139

Since 140

$$a_n = \frac{\Gamma(1+n+\beta)}{\Gamma(1+n+\alpha+\beta)} \frac{g^n(0)}{\Gamma(1+n)}$$

$$a_0 = \frac{48}{15\sqrt{\pi}}, a_1 = 0, a_2 = \frac{-640}{945\sqrt{\pi}}, a_3 = 0, a_4 = \frac{5376}{135135\sqrt{\pi}}$$

Thus the series solution of fractional initial value problem(15) is 141

$$y(t) = \frac{48}{15\sqrt{\pi}}t^{\frac{5}{2}} - \frac{640}{945\sqrt{\pi}}t^{\frac{9}{2}} + \frac{5376}{135135\sqrt{\pi}}t^{\frac{13}{2}} + \dots \tag{16}$$

3.2 One –term equation with nonzero initial condition. Consider the one-term fractional initial value problem. 142

$${}_0D_t^\alpha y(t) = f(t), y(0) = A, A \neq 0, t > 0, 0 < \alpha < 1. \tag{17}$$

Figure 3: Example 3.3

$${}_0\mathbf{D}_t^\alpha y(t) = f(t), [{}_0\mathbf{D}_t^{\alpha-1}y(t)]_{t=0} = \beta, \tag{25}$$

Where $t > 0, 0 < \alpha < 1$ and β is any constant.

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Let,

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$$y(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n t^{n+\alpha-1} \tag{26}$$

Be the solution of fractional initial value problem (25) Assume that $f(t)$ can be expanded in the Taylor series as

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$$f(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^n(0)}{\Gamma(n+1)} t^n, \text{ and } \frac{1}{\Gamma 0} = 0 \tag{27}$$

Using equation (26) and (27) in equation (25) and then applying formula (3), one obtains

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$$a_0 \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{\Gamma(0)} t^{-1} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_{(n+1)} \frac{\Gamma(n+\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(n+1)} t^n = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^n(0)}{\Gamma(n+1)} t^n.$$

Equating the coefficients of like powers of t , to yield

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$$a_{n+1} = \frac{f^n(0)}{\Gamma(n+1+\alpha)}, n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \tag{28}$$

To determine the coefficients a_0 , we use the initial condition $[{}_0\mathbf{D}_t^{\alpha-1}y(t)]_{t=0} = \beta$

$${}_0\mathbf{D}_t^{\alpha-1}y(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n {}_0\mathbf{D}_t^{\alpha-1}t^{n+\alpha-1} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n \frac{\Gamma(n+\alpha)}{\Gamma(n+1)} t^n = \beta$$

As $n \rightarrow 0$, we obtain $a_0 = \frac{\beta}{\Gamma(\alpha)}$. Therefore, the series solution of fractional initial value problem (25) is

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Figure 4: Example 3.4

$$y(t) = \frac{\beta}{\Gamma(\alpha)}t^{n-1} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^n(0)}{\Gamma(n + \alpha)}t^{n+\alpha-1}. \tag{29}$$

Example 3.4 : Consider one term fractional initial value problem 158

$${}_0\mathbf{D}_t^\alpha y(t) = cost, [{}_0\mathbf{D}_t^{-\frac{1}{2}} y(t)]_{t=0} = 1, t > 0. \tag{30}$$

Since $f(t) = cost, f'(t) = -sint, f''(t) = -cost, f'''(t) = sint, f^{iv}(t) = cost,$ 159

$$f(0) = 1, f'(0) = 0, f''(0) = -1, f'''(0) = 0, f^{iv}(0) = 1.$$

The coefficients can be determined as

$$a_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}}, a_1 = 0, a_2 = \frac{-1}{\Gamma\frac{7}{2}}, a_3 = 0, a_4 = \frac{1}{\Gamma\frac{11}{2}} \dots$$

Hence the series solution of fractional initial value problem (30) is 160

$$y(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} [1 - \frac{8}{15}t^{\frac{3}{2}} + \frac{16}{945}t^{\frac{7}{2}} + \dots] \tag{31}$$

4. Conclusion

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In conclusion, this paper has presented a novel approach utilizing the power series method to solve fractional differential equations. We have successfully introduced a new technique capable of finding exact solutions for fractional differential equations, extending our understanding beyond traditional integer-order differentials. Furthermore, we have demonstrated the applicability of our method to finite systems, showcasing its versatility and efficacy in various examples and real-world applications. The graphical representations provided offer additional insight into the behavior of solutions. Overall, our findings contribute to the advancement of techniques for solving fractional differential equations, opening up new avenues for research and practical applications in diverse fields.

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